

POSITIVE PSYCHOLOGICAL TRAITS: ANTECEDENTS TO TRANSFORMATIONAL LEADERSHIP STYLE

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Abstract

In the light of today's turbulent environment characterized by economic uncertainties, heightened geographical unrest, globalized, 24/7 competition, and never ending advanced technology. The pace of change in the work environment calls for a more positive outlook among the leaders. Challenging work/life situations facilitate the need for the development of positive behaviors among the leaders. It is transformational leadership that provides a better fit in leading the work groups in such a complex environment. The paper emphasises on how such leaders harness their own positive psychological strengths of hope, optimism, and resilience and set their table for success. The intent of this paper is to extend research on transformational leadership by examining potential determinants of transformational leadership and to generate some positive thinking and excitement in the field of Organizational Behaviour and to stimulate new theory building research and its effective application in the organizations. The study utilized the review of previous researches to allot antecedents to transformational leadership style. Analysis of secondary research reveals that hope, optimism and resilience are the determinants of transformational leadership. The organizations should strive to develop these positive factors in their leaders through leadership training programs. The avenue of future research is that the proposed antecedents should be empirically tested across countries or cultures to define the cultural impact.

Keywords: *Leadership, Performance, Positive Traits, Transformational Leadership Positive psychology*

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INTRODUCTION

Leadership is the capacity to translate vision into reality.

—Warren Bennis

Organizations all around the globe are deeply concerned with understanding, searching and developing leadership. Leadership is definitely not a ‘one-size-fits-all’ sort of word. It is one of those words that is ceaselessly debated and typically elicits a spectrum of individual opinions, from describing personality attributes, ‘position’ characteristics, or even behaviours. Whatever the arena be – sports, politics, religion, business, education – a leader impacts and influences organizational effectiveness. More than two decades ago, our understanding of leadership in organizations was dominated by the classic two factor approach focussing on task and relationship behaviors. Today, effective leadership is central to the organizational success. Notion of today’s leader is bigger, faster, better and more. Leadership is defined “not as what the leader does but rather as a process that engenders and is the result of relationships-relationships that focus on the interactions of both leaders and collaborators instead of focussing on only the competencies of the leaders” (Hernez-Broome & Hughes, 2004, p.27). In a competitive business environment, effective leadership is an essential requirement in order to achieve organisational goals. To do this, leaders must be able to provide inspiration, motivation and clear direction to their team. In the absence of effective leadership, organisations often grow slowly and may lose their direction and competitiveness.

Traditional view on leadership effectiveness has focussed primarily, although not extensively on what Burns (1978); Bass (1985) have called transactional leader behaviors. According to Burns (1978) transactional leaders are found on an exchange process in which the leaders provide rewards in return for the subordinate’s effort. More, recently, however, the focus of leadership research has shifted from one of examining the effects of transactional leadership to the identification and examination of those behaviors exhibited by the leader and make followers’ more aware of the importance and values of task outcomes, activate their higher order needs, and induce them to transcend self-interests for the sake of the organization (Bass, 1985; Yukl, 1989a, 1989b). These transformational or charismatic behaviors are believed to augment the impact of transactional leader behaviors on employee outcome variables, because “followers feel

trust and respect toward the leader and they motivate to do more than they are expected to do” (Yukl, 1989b, p.272).

Objective of the study:

Drawing on hope theory (Snyder, Harris et al., 1991) optimism theory (Scheier & Carver, 1985) and resiliency theory (Masten, 2001; Masten & Reed, 2002), the present study formulates a premise based on the positive psychological traits of hope, optimism and resiliency as potential antecedents to transformational leadership. The intent of this study is:

- To analyze how transformational leaders harness their own positive psychological strengths of hope, optimism, and resilience and set their table for success.
- To extend research on transformational leadership by examining potential determinants of transformational leadership.

Literature Review:

The following section deals with the previous researches to define the concepts of transformational leadership style, positive psychological traits such as hope, optimism and resilience and their relationships with transformational leadership style.

Transformational Leadership:

Literature defines transformational leadership as a motivational leadership style that involves presenting a clear organisational vision and inspiring employees to work towards the vision through establishing connections with them, understanding their needs, and helping them reach their potential and contributing to good outcomes for an organisation (Fitzgerald & Schutte, 2010). The transformational style of leadership aims to improve performance by encouraging followers to think beyond self interests by challenging them to achieve what was once thought impossible (Bass & Avolio, 1993; Bass & Riggio, 2006). Based on this premise, the researcher suggests that leaders who are positive in future outlook will engage in transformational leadership behaviors. Accordingly, those individuals who can harness their own positive psychological strengths of hope, optimism, and resilience will be most likely to demonstrate a transformational leadership style of leadership (Peterson et al., 2009).

Positive Psychological Traits

Given the pace of change in the work environment leaders need to be more positive in their approaches. Leaders should carry positive traits such as optimism, satisfaction, hope, meaning, and flow. Challenging work/life situations are integrally related to the need for and development of positive behaviors. Today, Organizations are seeking ways to help leaders and employees by recognising the importance of positivity and concentrating on developing their strengths. Positive psychological traits represent the extent to which individuals tend to be hopeful, optimistic and resilient in general. Although other positive psychological traits have been identified, however, the researcher focuses on hope, optimism and resiliency. The focus is on these three positive psychological traits in part because theory and research suggest these capacities to be positively related to enduring outcomes such as job performance and problem solving (Luthans, Avolio, Walumbwa & Li, 2005; Peterson & Luthans, 2003). They have also been suggested to play important roles in leadership development (Luthans & Avolio, 2003).

Hope Resource

The hope construct in positive psychology has considerable theoretical development, research support and is considered to be goal directed (Snyder, 1994). Hope is defined as a “positive motivational state that is based on an interactively derived sense of successful (1) agency (goal directed energy) and (2) pathways (planning to meet goals)” (Snyder, Irving & Anderson, 1991, p.287). Specifically, hope is the agreement of the agency, or goal directed energy/ willpower, and the pathways, the ways to achieve goals (Snyder, Irving, et al., 1991). In other words, hope consists of both willpower (individuals’ determination/ agency to achieve their goals) and “way power” thinking (being able to devise alternative pathways and contingency plans to achieve a goal in the face of obstacles) (Avey, Luthans & Jensen, 2009).

Optimism Resource

Carver & Scheier (2002, p.231) noted that “optimists are people who expect good things to happen to them, pessimists are people who expects bad things to happen to them” as optimists “differ in how they approach problems and challenges and differ in the manner and success with which they cope with adversity. Optimism is realistic and flexible (e.g. see Luthans, Youssef, et al., 2007; Schneider, 2001). Seligman (1998) defines an optimistic explanatory style as one that

attributes positive events to personal, lasting and persistent causes, and negative events to external, temporary and situation specific ones.

Resilience Resource

Resilience “refers to a class of phenomena characterized by patterns of positive adaptation in the context of significant adversity or risk” which enables individuals to bounce back effectively from adverse situations (Masten & Reed, 2002, p.75). Stewart, Reid & Mangham (1997) defined resiliency as “the capability of individuals to cope successfully in the face of significant change, adversity or risk. This capability changes over time and is enhanced by protective factors in the individual and environment” (p.22). The development of resilience is vital to help individuals recover from adversity or personal setbacks when they happen (Avey, Luthans & Jensen, 2009).

Positive Psychological Traits and Transformational Leadership

Transformational leadership has five dimensions (Bass & Avolio, 1995): Idealized Influence attributes, idealized influence behaviors, inspirational motivation, intellectual stimulation and individualized consideration. *Idealized Influence* refers to the extent to which a leaders demonstrate behaviours that allow them to serve as role models for their followers. Followers view their leaders as having extraordinary capabilities, persistence, risk taking, consistency and determination. They can be counted on to do the right things as they demonstrate high standards of ethical and moral conduct. It comprises of *Attribute* (leaders’ instil pride in others, go beyond self interest, display sense of power and confidence) and *Behaviors* (leaders’ instil strong sense of purpose, considers moral and ethical consequences of a decisions emphasize the importance of having collective sense of mission, values and beliefs). *Inspirational Motivation* refers to ability of the leaders to demonstrate behaviors that inspire and arouse team spirit, enthusiasm and optimism those around them by providing meaning and challenge to their followers’ work. *Intellectual Stimulation* refers to the ability of leaders to promote innovation and creativity by questioning assumptions, reframing problems, and approaching old situations in new ways *Individual Consideration* refers to the ability of leaders to pay special attention to each follower’s needs for achievement and growth and cater to their needs by being an effective listener.

Hope and Transformational Leadership

Transformational leaders trigger positive changes in their organization (Bass, 1998). Hopeful individuals have a high degree of confidence in their ability to stimulate change, by creating the multiple pathways along with the energy or agency that drives them to bring that change (Snyder, Harris et al., 1991). This confidence is likely to generate inspiration and motivation among their followers with respect to their vision. Hopeful leaders are always committed to their goals and take failures positively and demonstrate behaviors of idealized influence. Furthermore, pathways thinking will encourage leaders to design multiple alternative strategies when one confirms to be difficult and these thought provoking scenarios are associated with intellectual stimulation. Hopeful leaders also imagine numerous pathways for responding to any scenario or employee emotional state (Luthans & Youssef, 2007). Once a clear path has been tailored to the specific needs of each subordinate, leaders can then provide the needed individualized consideration to help them attain their goals (Peterson et al., 2009). Given the reasons, it seems likely that more hopeful leaders will be better at demonstrating the dimensions of transformational leadership (Bass, 1998).

Optimism and Transformational Leadership

Optimistic leaders envision and portray a positive future to their followers. Transformational leadership necessitates that leaders have a positive and the inspirational vision (Bass, 1998). Their conviction that good things will happen may also foster their belief that change is possible and positive (Peterson et al., 2009). First, given that optimistic people seek out more pleasant scenarios and ignore negative stimuli. Even in the face of negative circumstances, they remain upbeat and enthusiastic (Seegerstrom et al., 1998). Leaders who have these qualities are likely to inspire confidence in their followers' which is an important element of idealized influence. Second, it appears that leaders would need to have a positive outlook for the future to be inspiring and motivational toward others. In addition to their more positive outlook in general, optimists have found to approach problem differently than do the less optimistic. Optimists exhibit more active and creative approaches towards problem solving, they motivate and challenge their followers to do the same, thereby providing both intellectual stimulation and inspirational motivation to their followers (Peterson et al., 2009). Last, optimists have been showing to have more satisfying and stronger relationships with others (Srivastava, McGonigal, Richards, Butler & Gross, 2006). According to Peterson et al., (2009) it seems plausible that

leaders who have stronger relationships with their followers and feel more supported by them will be more likely to, in-turn provide needed support and individualized consideration to them.

Resilience and Transformational Leadership

Transformational leadership always focus on bringing about positive changes for one’s organization (Bass, 1998) more resilient leaders may be better prepared for inevitable setbacks and failures. First, resilient individuals not only cultivate positive emotions in themselves but also are skilled at eliciting positive emotions in relevant others (Werner & Smith, 1992). The dissemination of resilience, especially during trying times, may help to motivate and inspire others. Conger & Kanungo (1987) argued that leaders utilize emotions to arouse motivation and feelings in their followers. Accordingly, more resilient leaders are likely to be higher in inspirational motivation. Similarly, more resilient leaders’ confidence and demonstrated capabilities in rebounding from setbacks are likely to lead their followers to hold them in high regard. More resilient individuals have been found to experience higher well being (Tugade & Fredrickson, 2004). Therefore, Peterson et al. (2009) believed that their clear and confident vision of the future is likely to be positively related to idealized influence. Because resilient leaders are more confident in their ability to deal with failure, they may be more likely to encourage employees to take risks and to pursue innovative and creative activities. For example, the intellectual stimulation dimension, which refers to the leaders’ ability to motivate followers to meet their potential, may be enhanced by leaders’ resiliency.

Method and Findings:

The objective of the paper was to determine the potential inputs to transformational leadership style. For which the study utilized the secondary or desk research that involved summary, collation or synthesis of existing research. The information has been collected from various sources such as books and journals. The analysis of previous researches provided useful insights to determine the antecedents of transformational leadership style. The results reveal that how such leaders harness their own positive psychological strengths of hope, optimism, and resilience and set their table for success i.e. hope, optimism and resilience are found to be the determinants of transformational leadership. Figure 1, illustrates the antecedents to transformational leadership.

Figure 1. A model of antecedents of transformational leadership style

Limitations and Scope for Future Researches:

One valid critique is that there is too much emphasis in positive psychology in the individual and too little focus on positive societies, institutions and situations. It does not consider the impact of neighbourhoods, social groups, organizations or government in shaping the positive behaviors. Therefore, future researches should consider the impact of external factors such as societies, institutions and situations. Since, the study does not consider the effect of other variables on positive psychological traits that act as moderators in defining the leadership style. There is a need to continue exploring the moderators and mediators that increase or decrease the effects of positive psychological factors in the transformational leadership styles. Also, the study only pertains to secondary research as there is no first hand data collection. Therefore, the other avenue of future research should be that the proposed antecedents can be empirically tested across countries or cultures to define the cultural impact. The study focuses on only three psychological capacities, thus, for future researches, variations of the above developmental framework can be tested, and so can other potential positive psychological resource capacities besides hope, optimism and resilience.

Conclusion:

The research suggests that leaders who are positive in future outlook will engage in transformational leadership behaviors. Those individuals who can harness their own positive psychological strengths of hope, optimism, and resilience will be most likely to demonstrate a transformational leadership style of leadership. Overall, the issue of transformational leadership style and positive psychological resources appears to be worthy of an additional study. The rate of change in organizations and the demands of the turbulent environments do not appear to be

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slowing down, thereby necessitating a better understanding of how to enhance leaders’ positive psychological traits. A superior insight into how to boost leader levels of hope, optimism and resiliency in the face of increasing demands and in never ending turmoil and flux is required.

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